

THE ANALYSIS OF IDIOMS AND EXPRESSIONS IN ENGLISH

Azilova Zarnigor

410-group, 4th year student of the Foreign Language and Literature department
Berdakh Karakalpak State University

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Abstract. *The article talks about expressions, idioms and their meanings in the English language, specific expressions, culture and mentality of the English people.*

Key words: *phraseology, expression, idiom, proverb and sayings, tradition.*

АНАЛИЗ ИДИОМ И ВЫРАЖЕНИЙ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

Аннотация. *В статье говорится о выражениях, идиомах и их значениях в английском языке, специфических выражениях, культуре и менталитете английского народа.*

Ключевые слова: *фразеология, выражение, идиома, пословица и поговорка, традиция.*

Today, English is a global language. We cannot carry out international communication without learning and knowing it. In the process of learning this language, the language learner faces many difficulties, and the customs, mentality and interests of the people of this language are also formed. In the process of learning English, phraseological expressions, idioms and proverbs, and the study of culture also play an important role. This, in turn, helps in the formation of intercultural relations. A sense of respect for each other's traditions, values and history is formed between people. The proverbs and sayings reflect the way of thinking, world view, lifestyle, spirit and nature of the people, and the secrets of faith. Knowing them helps to better understand the people. It might be difficult when we are learning a new language understanding conversation, If people use some types of phrases as shortcuts to meaning. “For example, what would you think if a friend wants “to chew the fat” over a coffee? Would you expect to spend your lunchtime eating a piece of fat? No need to panic, that person has used an idiom. What is an idiom? An idiom is: A group of words (or a phrase) that have a meaning that is different from the meanings of the individual words (e.g. over the moon, see the light)”.¹

There are approximately 25,000 idioms in the English language. This might seem for you some daunting but you will soon know the most common ones of them by learning. Also you will be more confident when you use them in a conversation with somebody.

“Idioms are different from proverbs and sayings which are typically full-sentence compact expressions of folk wisdom (e.g. East or West home is best). It should be noted, however, that scholars often modify the scope of this notion so that it suits their research designs. It is thus always necessary to consider carefully specific approaches used by every individual author and find out what exactly the term conveys in a specific study”.²

Why idioms are important for us when we are learning some language? Idioms help us to improve our knowledge of English. Idioms are fixed expressions whose meanings are not

¹ Londonschool.com

² English phraseology and corora, Vilnius, 2017. 27-28p

immediately obvious from looking at the individual words in the idiom. We come across to many idioms when we listen or read something in English. So, they are important and we should learn about their meanings of idioms and about how they are used for understanding them.

“If you ask me: "Can there be miracles in the language?" - if they asked, I would have answered: "If so, the "miracle" of the language is its proverbs, sayings and idioms.)”³

Idioms are units of each language that are unique to each language and cannot be exactly translated into other languages, only equivalents (alternatives) can be used. Each nation has its own concepts. These concepts are important for one nation and may be completely incomprehensible for another nation. For example, let's pay attention to the following words of the Russians, they kiss their children and say "Здравствуйте, мои поросятюшки". However, if we translate it literally into Uzbek, it will be in the form: "Hello, my pigs", which is not typical for Uzbeks, because Uzbeks do not use the name "pig" for petting. , this word has a completely opposite meaning. If this concept is expressed in Uzbeks as: "Hello, my lambs (mares, my sheep)", then a good equivalent is chosen for the representatives of both languages, because in every nation goodness, virtue, evil, cunning, Various animals, birds or other objects were chosen as symbols of hypocrisy. Pig has a positive meaning for Russians, but not for Uzbeks. Therefore, idioms are units with similar meanings:

I was going to buy a ticket to see Taylor Swift, but it cost an arm and a leg. "It costs an arm and a leg".

If we translate this idiom literally, we get the meaning of an arm and a leg. One may wonder why an arm and a leg are needed in this place. I think the British use this idiom in so many ways that you can't even count your fingers and toes. When will there be peace and prosperity across the whole world? When pigs fly! In this sentence, when asked when there will be peace and prosperity in the whole world, the answer is when pigs fly. Now let's think logically and imagine a pig. Is there such an animal? Yes there is, but does it have any wings to fly? No, it only has legs to move on the ground. So it can never fly and we can assume that this event will never happen. A similar idiom exists in the Uzbek language and it is as follows: When the camel's tail touches the ground. It goes without saying that anyone who has seen, known and heard of a camel also knows that a camel's tail never touches the ground, and this is used for an event that will never happen. So, the Uzbek people have an idiom with the same meaning as the idiom of the English people.

Phraseological expressions are united under the terms: set-phrases, idioms, word-groups and phraseological units. Even today they are treated differently. “The richness of vocabulary of every language depends on not only the ways of forming new words, but also on the permanent idioms it may form. The science which studies the ‘world’ of those units is called phraseology. Phraseology is the science about idioms, and it was firstly used in 1928 by Y.D. Polovinov.”⁴

³ O'zbek tili. 10-sinf uchun darslik. –T.: 2022 122-b.

⁴ Amosova N.N. Fundamentals of English phraseology. – L; LGU, 1963.– 208 p.

Phraseological expressions are interesting in all languages. By translating them literally, we cannot understand their exact meaning. Often they depend on the history of that nation. Here are some examples of them: "Go bananas".

If we translate it literally into Uzbek, it means "Borish bananlar yoki Bananlar borish". But its original meaning in English is to be angry and angry. "Apples and oranges"

It is "Olmalar va apelsinlar" in Uzbek. From this we can think what a phrase can be and understand simple fruits. But the English people use this phrase to express different meanings.

To sum up, each nation has its own proverbs and sayings, idioms, expressions that reflect its own way of life, mentality, and customs. Therefore, it is difficult to understand the customs and mentality of a nation without knowing them to a certain extent. If we only translate them into our mother tongue by learning and knowing the language, we will not be able to understand the original meanings reflected in them.

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